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BOTTOM-UP INNOVATION IN A TOP-DOWN FRAMEWORK: RIS3 AND SOCIAL GOVERNANCE IN RURAL TERRITORIES

Abstract. This article examines the tensions between the Smart Specialisation Strategy (RIS3) as a public policy for territorial innovation and the emerging practices of social innovation in rural contexts. Through a case study of the municipality of Valverde de Burguillos (Spain), the study compares institutional top-down logic of RIS3 with the forms of relational governance and social capital that sustain community-based initiatives. Research suggests the need to reterritorialize RIS3 through frameworks more sensitive to local needs and know-how.

1. Introduction. Innovation has become a transversal concept in public policy, but its meaning and purpose vary depending on the adopted approach. In Europe, RIS3 has emerged as a key instrument to drive regional development through the identification of competitive advantages. However, several studies point out that its implementation has often been shaped by sectoral, technocratic, and urban-centered logics [1–4]. This article builds on a critical hypothesis: there is a clear disconnection between the institutional conception of innovation promoted by RIS3 and the actual community dynamics driving social change on the ground.

2. RIS3 and Situated Innovation: Conflicting Frameworks. RIS3 (Research and Innovation Strategies for Smart Specialisation) is an EU policy framework that promotes regional innovation by encouraging areas to invest in their distinctive strengths. Grounded in the quadruple helix model [5], it seeks to build cooperation between government, business, academia, and civil society. However, its implementation often reflects top-down governance and technocratic planning, with limited space for community participation or local knowledge [6,7]. By contrast, social innovation arises from bottom-up, contextual processes, reconfiguring collective life through cooperation, trust, and situated agency [8,9].

3. Valverde de Burguillos: A Local Innovation Experience. The rural municipality of Valverde de Burguillos (Extremadura, Spain), with fewer than 300 inhabitants, illustrates how small communities can generate social innovation through initiatives such as Ageing at Home, heritage recovery, and academic partnerships

[10,11]. These efforts rely on dense social capital [12,13]. The local network combines bonding, bridging, and linking forms of capital [14,15]. Yet such innovations remain largely invisible to RIS3 frameworks, which privilege standardized, market-driven indicators [16].

4. Discussion: Reterritorializing RIS3. The Valverde case reveals a disconnect between formal innovation strategies and the actual processes occurring in the territory. While RIS3 conceptualizes territorial development through innovation, its focus remains primarily on productive sectors, often overlooking the relational ecosystems that enable change [17,18]. Reterritorializing RIS3 requires recognizing social capital as soft infrastructure for innovation. This involves moving beyond the measurement of competitive advantages toward identifying community-based organizational capacities, often invisible in conventional evaluation frameworks [4,19].

5. Conclusions. As a public policy instrument, RIS3 faces the challenge of incorporating territorial complexity into its design and implementation. The case of Valverde de Burguillos demonstrates that innovation takes place beyond official frameworks and that rural communities possess the organizational capacity to sustain meaningful transformations.

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UNLOCKING SUSTAINABLE GROWTH: A DATA ANALYTICS FRAMEWORK FOR ADVANCING COMMUNICATION STRATEGIES IN THE MOLDOVAN WINE SECTOR

Abstract: the development of the wine sector is a priority of the national policy of the Republic of Moldova. Given the importance of this sector for the Moldovan economy, its sustainable development should be carefully planned and constantly adapted to emerging innovations in this field. Analytics is an important consideration in developing strategic directions for the sector, and has been changing significantly over the past few years due to the impact of advanced technology. New tools allow the development of many alternative approaches that will be relevant to different strategic approaches.

Keywords: wine sector, analytics, communication strategies, optimization.

Introduction. The wine industry is an important part of Moldova's economy, and the country aims to strengthen its position on the world stage by positioning itself as the "Global Wine Capital 2025". To achieve sustainable growth and increase